

SLIDE 1

THE TECHNOLOGICAL APPLICATION USE IN LANGUAGE LEARNING PERCEIVED BY THE STUDENTS IN EFL CLASSROOM

**ABDUL GAFUR MARZUKI – IAIN PALU
SANTIANA – UNIVERSITAS SILIWANGI**

**International Conference on English, Language and Literature
(ICELL) Makassar, November 7-8, 2020**

Abdul Gafur Marzuki - Santiana

BACKGROUND

1

**Merdeka Belajar
Concept**

2

**Learning during
Pandemic Covid-
19 Era**

Educational Technology on ELT

Reasons for Integrating technology on ELT

Integrating YouTube, Kahoot, Video Recording

Why Use YouTube?

Reason 1

- ❖ Source of materials
- ❖ Students may post their job
- ❖ Suitable for autonomous learning principles
- ❖ Encouraging and engaging the students

Reason 2

- We have to educate the students, we must:
- ❖ Adapt to their world
 - ❖ Adapt to their learning styles

Reason 3

- We must know they are millennial:
- ❖ Hyper communicators
 - ❖ Gadget oriented
 - ❖ The most used by the students

The Benefit of Utilizing YouTube

Global connection

Enhances the comprehension of complex topics

Creates more engagement from students

Ideal for slow learners

One teacher, multiple classrooms

Ways of Utilizing Youtube

Help the struggling students

Trigger unique and interesting discussions

Allow students to gain in-depth information

Access high quality education materials for free

Flip lessons

Review for exams

Utilizing Kahoot as a Learning Tool

...

Utilizing Video Recording as a learning tool

...

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design Survey-Qualitative

1

Instruments

- ❖ Questionnaire
- ❖ Interview

2

3

- Participants
- ❖ 50 Students

FINDINGS

The findings showed that the use of technology in EFL learning offer benefit to improving students' language learning experience with practicing the language in a real-life context.

- Facebook benefits the students to freely express an opinion and participate in a discussion.
- Kahoot supports the students to enrich their vocabulary and language expression.
- Voice recordings can let the students produce appropriate pronoun.

CONCLUSION

Technology in education can be used for different purposes. It can be used as a tutor, as a teaching tool, and as a learning tool. This study has focused on integrating technology as teaching and learning tools, in this case, YouTube, Kahoot, and video recording. The students possessed a positive response towards the utilizing of technology in EFL learning because it offers benefits to improve students' language learning experience concerning practicing the language in a real life context. They have acquired new English words and phrases and developed their language skills simultaneously.

Abdul Gafur Marzuki - Santiana

References

1. Albana, H. H., Marzuki, A. G., Alek, A., & Hidayat, D. N. (2020). Cohesive Devices in Student's Writing (A Discourse Analysis on Argumentative Text). *Jurnal Pendidikan Humaniora*, 8(1), 6-11.
2. Alek, A., Marzuki, A. G., Farkhan, M., & Deni, R. (2020). Self-Assessment in Exploring EFL Students' Speaking Skill. *Al-Ta lim Journal*, 27(2), 208-214.
3. Alek, A., Marzuki, A. G., Farkhan, M., Surahman, D., Daryanto, D., & Febrianto, S. (2020). Computer Based Testing in Senior High School on National Examination. *Indonesian Journal of Learning Education and Counseling*, 2(2), 204-210.
4. Alek, A., Marzuki, A. G., Hidayat, D. N., & Sari, E. N. A. (2020). A Critical Discourse Analysis of song "Look What You Made Me Do" by Taylor Swift. *Eralingua: Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa Asing dan Sastra*, 4(2), 154-161.
5. Alek, A., Marzuki, A. G., Hidayat, D. N., Islamiati, F. A., & Raharjo, A. R. (2020). "Why She Disappeared"(A Study of Illeism in Poetic Discourse). *Ethical Lingua: Journal of Language Teaching and Literature*, 7(2), 447-453.
6. Fatimah, A. S., & Santiana, S. (2017). Teaching in 21st century: Students-teachers' perceptions of technology use in the classroom. *Script Journal: Journal of Linguistic and English Teaching*, 2(2), 125.
7. Fatimah, A. S., Santiana, S., & Saputra, Y. (2019). Digital Comic: An Innovation of Using Toondoo as Media Technology for Teaching English Short Story. *English Review: Journal of English Education*, 7(2), 101-108.
8. Haucsa, G. M., Marzuki, A. G., Alek, A., & Hidayat, D. N. (2020). Illocutionary Speech Acts Analysis in Tom Cruise's Interview. *Academic Journal Perspective: Education, Language, and Literature*, 8(1), 11-19.

9. Iftitah, A. N., Marzuki, A. G., & Kuliahana, A. (2020). DEVELOPING VOCABULARY MASTERY THROUGH GUESSING WORDS GAME FOR THE SEVENTH GRADE STUDENTS OF SMP NEGERI 10 PALU. *Datokarama English Education Journal*, 1(1), 19-37.
10. Kuliahana, A., & Marzuki, A. G. (2020). Repetition Technique in an EFL Speaking Class in Islamic Higher Education in Indonesia. *Academic Journal Perspective: Education, Language, and Literature*, 8(1), 20-28.
11. Marzuki, A. G. (2019). The Implementation of SQ3R Method to Develop Students' Reading Skill on Islamic Texts in EFL Class in Indonesia. *Register Journal*, 12(1), 49-61.
12. Marzuki, A. G. (2019). The Roles of School Principal Leadership in Developing English Teachers' Creativities in Palu. *Al-Ta'lim Journal*, 26(3), 267-279.
13. Marzuki, A. G. (2019). Utilizing Recorded English Dialogues in Teaching English Word Stress to Islamic Higher Education Students in Indonesia. *Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 5(1), 53-64.
14. Marzuki, A. G., & Kuliahana, A. (2021). Using Language Games to Enhance EFL Students' Speaking Skill in Indonesia. *Al-Ta'lim Journal*, 28(3), 213-222.
15. Marzuki, A. G., Alim, N., & Wekke, I. S. (2018). Improving the reading comprehension through cognitive reading strategies in language class of coastal area in indonesia. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 156(1), 012050). IOP Publishing.
16. Marzuki, A. G., Amelia, Y., & Syam, H. (2021). THE EFFECT OF ANXIETY TOWARD STUDENTS'LEARNING MOTIVATION OF THE ELEVENTH GRADE AT SMAN 4 PALU. *Datokarama English Education Journal*, 2(1), 49-57.
17. Marzuki, A. G., Santiana, A. K., Alek, N. F., Darmawati, B., & Bin-Tahir, S. Z. The Teaching of EFL Vocabulary through Anticipatory Learning Strategy in Islamic Higher Education Context in Indonesia.
18. Marzuki, A.G. (2016b). Utilizing cooperative learning in islamic college students' classroom, *IJEE (Indonesian Journal of English Education)*, 3(2), 123-139.
19. Marzuki, A.G. (2017). Developing speaking skill through oral report in an efl class in indonesia, *Al-Ta'lim Journal*, 24(3), 243-254.
20. Santiana, S., Lesmana, D. S., Marzuki, A. G., & Erizar, E. (2021, December). AN INSIGHT OF ANITALES APPS PERCEIVED BY DIGITAL STORYTELLING STUDENTS. In *Proceeding of International Conference on Islamic Education (ICIED) (Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 23-30)*.